

ECONOMIC ASPECTS OF TRANSITION TO INNOVATION ECONOMY

Samandar Berdikulov

Gulistan State University, Faculty of Digital Economy and Innovation, 2nd year student of
Accounting and Auditing

Inomjon Khabibullaev

3rd year student of Economics

Responsible for the article: alisher892jentra@gmail.com

mobile phone: +998-99-887-07-94

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10931193>

Abstract. *The article discusses the theoretical issues of forming a mechanism for managing the process of ensuring sustainable development. It is analyzed that the main factors of sustainable development of the region arise from the need to transition to an innovative economic model and, therefore, to ensure the process of managing innovative activities. Also, the structure of the innovation activity management mechanism in the region is justified, and a diagram of the relationship between the main processes is presented.*

Key words: *region, sustainable economic development, innovative activity, management of innovative activity.*

ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ПЕРЕХОДА К ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются теоретические вопросы формирования механизма управления процессом обеспечения устойчивого развития. Анализируется, что основные факторы устойчивого развития региона возникают из необходимости перехода к инновационной модели экономики и, следовательно, обеспечения процесса управления инновационной деятельностью. Также обоснована структура механизма управления инновационной деятельностью в регионе и представлена схема взаимосвязи основных процессов.*

Ключевые слова: *регион, устойчивое экономическое развитие, инновационная деятельность, управление инновационной деятельностью.*

Relevance of the topic. Currently, the problem of sustainable development makes new economic relations more relevant. First of all, this is related to the increase of uncertainty and instability of internal and external processes and events. Secondly, with the development of global conflicts based on the multifaceted crisis of society and economy. Thirdly, the problem of shortage

of natural resources is getting worse. In such conditions, the sustainable development of regional socio-economic systems in the long-term perspective can be mainly related to innovative development based on scientific and technical innovations that allow the use of new resources - knowledge in order to increase the efficiency of the economy. and ensuring competitiveness of regions. But the peculiarity of the present time is that the spread of new technologies exceeds the ability of existing institutions to manage and control innovation. On the one hand, technological innovation increases labor efficiency, expands the scope of interaction, etc., on the other hand, the acceleration of technological development increases social stratification, pressure on the environment and leads to structural changes, which leads to the loss of wages will bring.

The inconsistency of this process is that technological innovations that cause macro shifts destabilize established social institutions. It includes the identification of new approaches, factors, tools, methods and mechanisms of effective management of regional development, which will accordingly increase the living standards of the population of the regional socio-economic system and create a favorable environment (conditions) for regional development.

The purpose of the study is to substantiate the approach to the formation of an effective mechanism for managing the process of ensuring sustainable development in the context of the transition to an innovative economic model based on a new methodology of scientific and technical forecasting.

Analyzes within the subject. System control mechanism is understood as the process of influencing the controlled system to ensure its required behavior, affecting various parameters of the system [1], including:

- composition (participants included in the system, i.e. its elements);
- structure (a set of information, management, technological and other communications between system participants);
- a set of optimal strategies (constraints and activity norms) of system participants, including institutional, technological and other restrictions and their joint activity norms;
- benefits of system participants;
- awareness - information about important parameters that system participants have when making decisions on selected strategies;
- work procedure (sequence of obtaining information and choosing strategies by system participants).

The first basis of the classification system of systems control mechanisms (management decision-making procedures) is the control subject - a component of the system that changes the

control process and result. On this basis, we can distinguish the following: composition management; structure management; institutional management (management of restrictions and activity norms); motivational management (management of preferences and interests); information management (management of information available to system participants during decisionmaking); management of the operational procedure (control of the sequence of receiving information and the selection of strategies by participants).

The second basis for the classification system can also be the basis for expanding the basic model - the presence or absence of: dynamics; many interconnected agents; multi-level; distributed management; uncertainty; limitation of joint activity; informational messages.

The third basis of the classification system is the modeling method. Based on this, we can distinguish control mechanisms based on optimization and game-theoretic models.

The fourth basis of the classification system of system control mechanisms is the control functions, the implementation of which is provided by one or another mechanism. Therefore, according to the fourth basis of the classification system (management functions), we can distinguish planning mechanisms, organizational mechanisms, incentive mechanisms and control mechanisms.

The fifth basis is management tasks, the solution of which must be provided by a mechanism for managing this or that system.

Thus, the proposed bases and meanings of the characteristics of the classification system allow to uniformly describe both specific control mechanisms and their combinations - sets of control mechanisms. At the same time, it should be noted that each specific mechanism cannot always be clearly assigned to one or another class - in many cases, the same mechanisms solve different management problems and are used in different fields of application. can and so on.

During the analysis of the development of the regional socio-economic system, it was determined that the following factors should be taken into account among the factors of sustainable development of the regional socio-economic system in the context of the transition to the innovative model of the economy. Those listed in Table 1 are highlighted. The most important of them, from our point of view, are innovation and technology.

Thus, the development of the economy and the preservation of its competitiveness in the long-term perspective are inextricably linked with the development and introduction of innovations. In this regard, the creation of an innovative economic development mechanism is a priority task at both the state and regional management levels. The current task of the regions is to ensure sustainable socio-economic development on the basis of large-scale innovations and

investments and the task of forming a regional innovation system based on this, it is necessary to ensure the process of managing innovative activities.

The mechanism for managing innovative activity in the region should not be determined by the management process, because its task is to ensure this process and achieve the goal set by the management entity. That is, the innovative activity management mechanism exists and operates as an independent subsystem in the management system and is not synonymous with the management process. When considering the mechanism of management of innovative activity in the region, it should be taken into account that it acts as a means of practical implementation of management, because the essence of management on the object of management includes the organizational influence of the subject.

Based on the above, Figure 1 shows a schematic diagram of the process of managing innovative activity in the region and the role of the management mechanism as a means of exercising control over the management object.

The macro- and meso-level creates conditions for the effective functioning and development of all structures in the regional innovation system, and for solving relevant problems at the micro-level, that is, directly in organizations by internal management bodies.

A management object is a network of organizations that produce, create, help create and distribute innovations (elements of the regional innovation system), as well as cluster interaction between them.

The elements of the mechanism of management of innovative activity in the region, first of all, have the characteristic of being a structural, tool, representing the static side of management influence. Second, they are characterized by functionality, but do not include the operational environment, which includes laws, regulations, and other governance phenomena.

It is necessary to form appropriate criteria to distinguish the elements that directly constitute the mechanism of management of innovative activity in the region. Such a criterion may be the direct connection of the management mechanism with the process of development, adoption and implementation of management decisions as a means of exercising the control influence of the subject on the object of control. That is, it is not just elements of the management system, but a set of interconnected, well-defined control tools that work in a logical sequence, with the help of which optimal management decisions are made and effectively implemented in the management process. . management of innovative activities. That is, the implementation of the interaction between the subject and the object of control, taking into account the available resources and the need for the subject to control the object through control actions based on compliance with principles,

performance of functions and management and means there are opportunities. use of methods of joint management.

Science-based suggestions and recommendations. Thus, the mechanism for managing innovative activity in the region is, firstly, a set of management tools that includes three main interrelated components, with the help of which reasonable management decisions are made and their effective implementation is ensured, namely: principles, functions and management methods; secondly, a method of purposefully changing the model of organizational behavior of the subjects of the regional innovation system and the model of the behavior of consumers of innovative products by creating an effective communication environment and using a set of forecasting and post-forecasting management tools.

By predictive management, we mean the ability to see the composition of future events based on the results of forecasting the development of the region using economic, mathematical and simulation models. Post-forecast management is a system of actions aimed at correcting future events, simultaneously improving them, as well as transferring knowledge about them.

Taking into account the approaches proposed in the literature, the mechanism of management of innovative activity in the region includes a set of management principles, which can be divided into three components: general, general system and private.

The general principles of management include objectively existing universal principles, including: balanced centralization-decentralization, the optimal combination of command and collegiality, delegation of authority and responsibility, initiative and remuneration, hierarchy, subordination, etc. [2].

REFERENCES

1. Novikov D.A. Teoriya upravleniya organizatsionnymi system. — M.: MPSI, 2005.
2. Gosudarstvennoe upravlenie: slovar-spravochnik / Pod ed. L.T. Volochkovoy, L.B. Kuznetsova, V.N. Mininoy, M. Holtsera, Dj. Shafritsa. —SPb.:OOO. Izd-vo "Petropolis", 2001.
3. Innovative type of economic development: Uchebnik. Izd. 2-e, dop. i pererab. /Pod obshch. ed. A.N. Folomeva. — M.: Izd-vo RAGS, 2008.
4. Burkhanov A.Kh. Agricultural economics, textbook 2022, "Ziya publishing house", Sirdaryo Pirint. Page 630.
5. Burxanov, A. (2023). QISHLOQ XO ‘JALIGIDA INNOVATSIYON IQTISODIYOTGA O ‘TISHNING ZAMONAVIY MUAMMOLARI. Iqtisodiyot va ta’lim, 24(4), 37-42.

6. Бурханов, А. (2023). Сущность и особенности новых экономических отношений в сельском хозяйстве. *Economics and Innovative Technologies*, 11(2), 166-179.
7. Hakimova, M. Kh. "THE EFFECT OF FACTORS ON THE NUMERICAL INDICATIONS OF MICROORGANISMS IN IRRIGATED LIGHT COLORED GRAY AND BARRIOUS SOILS." (2024).